

Hardware/Software Co-design and Verification Methodology from System Level Based on System Dependence Graph

Shunsuke Sasaki¹, Tasuku Nishihara,
Daisuke Ando, Masahiro Fujita

(University of Tokyo, Japan

{shun, tasuku, ando}@cad.t.u-tokyo.ac.jp, fujita@ee.t.u-tokyo.ac.jp)

Abstract: System Dependence Graph (SDG) is a graph representation which shows dependencies among statements / expressions in a design. In this paper, we propose a new HW/SW co-design methodology based on SDG. In our method, any combination of C / C++ / SpecC descriptions is acceptable as input designs so that design functions can be specified flexibly. First, the input descriptions are analyzed and verified with static but partially dynamic program checking methods by traversing SDG. With those methods, large descriptions can be processed. Next, those designs are divided into HW and SW parts. In this step, SDGs are fully utilized to insert parallelism into the designs, and it enables flexible HW/SW partitioning. The HW parts are further optimized and then converted into RTL descriptions by existing behavioral synthesis tools. Finally, the generated RTL descriptions together with the SW parts are compared to the original descriptions in order to make sure that they are logically equivalent. Also, designer-specified properties may be model checked with these final design descriptions. Such formal verifications can be realized by translating those descriptions into Finite State Machine (FSM) type representations and existing formal verifiers. We show two case studies with practical examples to demonstrate the usefulness of our approach.

Key Words: program slicing, hardware software co-design, hardware software co-verification

Category: B.7.2, D.2.2, D.2.4

1 Introduction

Due to the advances in VLSI and System-on-a-Chip (SoC) technology, the complexity of the fabricated chips is growing rapidly. The design and verification of SoC, however, do not catch up with such the quick growth. This makes the efficiency gap between the production and design / verification much wider, which is one of the key problems in today's SoC design market. Now, new design methodologies which make the design and verification processes much more productive, are highly required. One of the most effective ways to improve design productivity is to start design from more abstracted levels. Recently, several system-level design languages which support IP reuse, such as SpecC [SpecC] or SystemC [SystemC], have been proposed. In system-level design, not only hardware (HW) development but also software (SW) development is taken care of.

¹ Now at Toshiba Corporation

Program slicing is a technique which extracts portions related to a specified portion in a design [Weiser 1984]. It is originally developed in SW field, but also extended for HW field [Tanabe et al. 2004, Clarke et al. 1999]. This technique is known to be very useful in various ways for SW and HW development, e.g. program analysis, maintenance, debugging, test, and reuse. System Dependence Graph (SDG) is an intermediate graph representation for program slicing, and represents dependencies among statements / expressions in a design.

In this paper, we propose a HW/SW co-design methodology based on SDG. We use the SDG proposed in [Tanabe et al. 2004], and it can be created from any combination of C / C++ / SpecC descriptions. In the proposed methodology, information of dependencies represented by the SDG is fully utilized for static (partially dynamic) code checking, parallelism extraction for HW/SW partitioning, and formal verification.

This paper is the extended version of [Sasaki et al. 2006], and the following points were refined from it.

- Deadlock and race condition detection methods were appended.
- The detail of the HW/SW partitioning method was described.
- Sufficient experimental results were appended.

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows. Section 2 introduces background knowledge on existing techniques used in our method and related works. In Section 3, we give a proposed co-design methodology based on SDG. In Section 4, we show case studies of the proposed method by applying it to HW/SW co-designs of MPEG2 decoder and JPEG2000 encoder and demonstrate the usefulness of our approach. Finally, we conclude this work in Section 5.

2 Background

2.1 SpecC

SpecC [SpecC] is a system-level design description language, which is an extension of ANSI-C language to describe HW parts of designs. In this section, we introduce the three main extensions in SpecC such as structural hierarchy, concurrency, and synchronization.

2.1.1 Structural Hierarchy

In order to describe structural hierarchies of target systems as classes in C++, *behavior*, *channel*, and *interface* are introduced in SpecC. A behavior has ports, component instantiations, private member variables and functions, and a public *main* member function. It can communicate with each other behaviors through

channels. An interface connects behaviors and a channel, and declarations of communication methods, which will be defined in channels, are described. One advantage of using SpecC is that designers can describe computation and communication separately.

2.1.2 Concurrency

Generally, statements in SpecC are executed sequentially from the top down as C / C++. Additionally, concurrent executions can be described in SpecC with *par* statements. Statements directly under a *par* statement are executed as concurrent processes.

2.1.3 Synchronization

Synchronizations among concurrent processes under a *par* statement can be represented by *wait* / *notify* statements and *event* variables. For any event variable e , an execution of *wait*(e) suspends the execution of the process until *notify*(e) is executed in the other concurrent processes.

2.2 System Dependence Graph (SDG)

An SDG of a program is a graph where each node represents a statement and each edge represents dependence between two statements. Dependence edges are mainly classified into data-dependence edges and control-dependence edges. A data dependence edge is drawn from an assignment node N_1 to another node N_2 if an assigned variable at N_1 can be used at N_2 . On the other hand, a control dependence edge is drawn from a control point node N_1 to another node N_2 if the execution of N_2 is controlled by N_1 (e.g. conditional branch). In addition, data dependence edges are labeled with the related variable, and control dependence edges are labeled with "true" or "false".

In [Tanabe et al. 2004], Tanabe et al. defined an SDG for SpecC descriptions. In the rest of this section, we introduce the detailed graph structures of the SpecC SDG. How concurrency and synchronization are represented in SDGs is also introduced.

2.2.1 Nodes and Edges

Table 1 shows the nodes and edges in the SpecC SDG. They are defined based on the SDG for C++ used in CodeSurfer[Grammatech] from Grammatech Inc. The nodes written in italic in the table were newly defined for SpecC.

Table 1: Nodes and Edges of SpecC SDG.

	Elements(Additional element)
Nodes	Entry
	Function / Behavior / Channel / Interface Entry
	Assignment
	Assignment, Notify
	Control Point
	if, while, for, switch, case, par, wait, fsm
	Call Site
	Function Call, Instance Call
	Actual Parameter
	Actual In, Actual Out, Global Actual In, Global Actual Out
	Formal Parameter
	Formal In, Formal Out, Global Formal in, Global Formal Out
	Return
	Return
	Declaration
	Declaration
Edges	Control
	Control, Call
	Data
	Data, Parameter In, Parameter Out
	Declaration
	Declaration

Figure 1: Dependence graph of `par`.

Figure 2: Dependence graphs of `wait` and `notify`.

2.2.2 Concurrency

Figure 1 gives an example of an SDG including concurrency. A **par** statement is represented as a **Control Point** node, which is similar to **if** or **while** statement. Control dependence edges are drawn from the **par** node to child nodes. All control dependence edges from the **par** node are marked as **true**.

2.2.3 Synchronization

Figure 2 gives an example of an SDG including synchronization. A **wait** statement is represented as a **Control Point** node, and control dependence edges are drawn from the **wait** node to all nodes before the next **Control Point** node. Also data dependence edges of event variables, which are the arguments of **notify** nodes, are drawn to the **wait** node from a **Formal In** node. On the other hand, a **notify** statement is represented as an assignment node, and a data dependence edge of the event variable, which is the argument of the notify node, is drawn to a **Formal Out** node which corresponds to the output value of the event variable from the behavior in which the notify node is. If synchronization is properly taken with **wait/notify**, a data dependence edge of an event variable used in a **notify** node always reaches to the corresponding **wait** node via **Formal In / Out**.

2.2.4 Program Slicing

Program slicing is a technique which extracts portions related to a specified portion in program codes. It is performed with SDG, and mainly there are three types of slicing techniques.

Backward slicing is a technique which extracts portions which affect a specified portion in program codes. It is performed by gathering nodes passed while traversing dependence edges backwardly from the specified nodes.

Forward slicing is a technique which extracts portions affected by a specified portion in program codes. It is performed by gathering nodes passed while traversing dependence edges forwardly from the specified nodes.

Chopping is a technique which extracts portions on the dependencies between two specified portions in program codes. It is performed by extracting the intersection of forward slicing from one portion and backward slicing from the other portion.

2.3 Static Checking with Program Checker

For SW programs written in C/C++ , many program checkers have been developed. To find bugs, data-flow analysis (DFA) is widely implemented in many tools like FlexeLint [FlexeLint], Coverity [Coverity], Fortify [Fortify], Orion

[Orion] and UNO [Holzmann 2002]. These tools show suspicious portions in a source code to programmers as warnings. However, since DFA is static and does not consider functionalities, many false-negative warnings are reported. This makes it difficult for programmers to identify real bugs from a large number of warnings. To reduce false-negative warnings, some tools check feasibilities that determine whether paths can actually be executed.

Compared with these checkers, our method can cover SpecC language, one of the system-level description languages, as well as ANSI-C.

2.4 Hardware/Software Partitioning

Partitioning a system into HW and SW is one of the important steps in the refinement process from system level. This step has been researched as methods to map tasks into HW and SW, and the complete optimization is known to be an NP complete problem. Recently, many researches for HW/SW optimization are done by heuristics [Knerr et al. 2004, Wiangtong et al. 2002].

However, in commercial use, designers usually decide where to be assigned to HW based on the results of performance estimation by simulation [Ueda et al. 2005]. One of the reasons why even though there are a lot of automatic HW/SW partitioning method, they are not widely used in commercial use, is that usually descriptions before HW/SW partitioning are not divided into multiple processes.

Therefore, we propose a method to divide a sequential process into multiple concurrent processes. Though our method does not change or optimize design behaviors, after applying our method, existing partitioning methods can be used more effectively. The detail of this method is described in Section 3.2.

After applying the proposed method, we can apply existing HW/SW partitioning methods to find the best result to assign the concurrent processes into HW and SW.

2.5 Formal Verification

Formal verification is the act of proving or disproving the correctness of a system with respect to a certain formal specification or property, using formal methods which are mathematically based techniques. Formal verification techniques can be classified into model checking (property checking) and equivalence checking.

Model checking [Clarke et al. 1986, McMillan 1993, Brand 1993] is a technique to algorithmically verify the model, often derived from a HW or SW design formally. This is achieved by checking if the model satisfies a logical specification (property). The property is often written as temporal logic formulae. Equivalence Checking [Brand 1993, Kuehlmann et al. 2002] verifies the functional equivalence of two designs that are at the same or different abstraction levels.

Formal verification methods for high-level HW descriptions or system level descriptions are now in study phase. [Sakunkonchak et al. 2005, Moy et al. 2005, Grobe et al. 2003, Grobe et al. 2004] present model checking methods that verify SpecC or SystemC descriptions. [Sakunkonchak et al. 2005, Moy et al. 2005] are targeting on synchronization properties such as deadlock. [Grobe et al. 2003, Grobe et al. 2004] check general properties written in temporal logic. Also, [Semeria et al. 2002, Clarke et al. 2003, Karfa et al. 2006, Saito et al. 2002, Matsumoto et al. 2006] show equivalence checking methods.

[Semeria et al. 2002, Clarke et al. 2003] check equivalences between behavioral level descriptions (ex. C descriptions) and Register Transfer Level (RTL) descriptions. In [Semeria et al. 2002], two descriptions are checked by a commercial RTL equivalence checker [Formality] after translating a behavioral description into an RTL description. [Clarke et al. 2003] checks equivalence by using a model checker as a verification engine. [Karfa et al. 2006, Saito et al. 2002, Matsumoto et al. 2006] check equivalence between two system level descriptions by symbolic simulation. Symbolic simulation is a common technique in HW verification and treats variables in descriptions as symbols rather than bit vectors.

Formal verification methods for RTL descriptions are matured technologies supported by commercial SW tools [SLEC, Solidify, Formality].

3 Our Method

Figure 3 shows an overview of our method.

Inputs of this method are any combinations of C/C++/SpecC descriptions, so that designers can specify functions of the HW/SW systems more flexibly.

As the first step, the input descriptions can be analyzed and verified with an SDG generated from the input descriptions. We give the details on this step in Section 3.1. Also, the model checking methods [Sakunkonchak et al. 2005, Moy et al. 2005, Grobe et al. 2003, Grobe et al. 2004] introduced in Section 2.5 can be applied as well in this step.

After the first step, we divide the systems into HW and SW parts after introducing parallelism. HW parts are synthesized into RTL descriptions. The details are given in Section 3.2.

As the last step, the divided and synthesized HW parts and the SW parts are compared to the original descriptions to check functional equivalence. Designer specified properties can also be checked by model checkers at this step. The details are given in Section 3.3.

3.1 Static Program Checking

First of all, we generate SDGs from the input design descriptions to analyze and verify them. In this section, we show several static program checking methods.

Figure 3: Overview of Our Method.

Although some checking methods have been proposed for other dependence graphs[Ferrante et al. 1987], those methods need to be re-discussed in this paper since our methods use SpecC SDG and can be used for system level designs which contain both HW and SW.

3.1.1 Detection of Unused Variables or Statements

Usually, each statement in design descriptions should have some influences on some outputs. Statements which have no effects on outputs include bugs with high probability. In order to detect such statements, backward slicing can be used.

The algorithm is as follows:

1. Backward slicing from each output statement is performed.
2. The intersection of the results is computed.

Figure 4: An example for detecting unused variables.

3. All nodes NOT included in the intersection have no effects on outputs, hence these nodes indicate unused variables or statements.

Figure 4 gives an example source code and its SDG with an unused variable “sxy” and an unused statement “sxy = x * y”. Control dependence edges are abbreviated for simplicity. This example has an output port “z”. In SpecC language, inputs and outputs are clearly indicated as ports. The gray colored nodes in Figure 4 are included in the result of backward slicing from the output node “int z”. The node “int sxy” and the node “sxy = x * y” are not included in the result of backward slicing, so we can detect them as unused variables/statements.

3.1.2 Detection of Uses of Uninitialized Variables

When the value of a variable is used in statements, the variable must be initialized before the executions of those statements. Uses of uninitialized variables are classified into three types as given in Figure 5. In each case, a variable “a” is used at a statement “b = a + 5”. However, in (a), there are no nodes initializing “a”. In (b), though “a = 0” initializes “a”, it may not be executed since it is under a conditional branch “if(cond)”. In (c), the execution order of “a = 0” and “b = a + 5” is not decidable when the behavior “B31” and “B32” are running concurrently. Therefore, “a” can be used before initializations in each case.

Uses of uninitialized variables can be detected by the following procedure.

1. For each variable used in a node, nodes where the variable is initialized are collected by traversing data dependence edges backwardly.
2. Whether at least one of the initializing nodes is always executed before the using node, is checked.

For example, a node “b = a + 5” in Figure 5 (b) is checked as follows.

1. A variable “a” is used in the node.

Figure 5: Classification of uses of uninitialized variables

2. Whether “a” is always initialized is checked.
 - (a) Data dependence edges about “a” are traversed backwardly from “b = a + 5”, and “a = 0” which initializes “a” is found.
 - (b) Whether “a = 0” is always executed is checked.
 - i. Control dependence edges are traversed backwardly from “b = a + 5” and “a = 0” to find the lowest common control node.
 - ii. Entry node “B2.main()” is found.
 - iii. “b = a + 5” is reachable from “B2.main()” along control dependence edges.
 - iv. “a = 0” is NOT reachable from “B2.main()” without passing the control node “if(cond)”.
 - v. Therefore, it is not guaranteed that “a = 0” is always executed.
 - (c) It is decided that “a” may be uninitialized.

Figure 6 gives the algorithm of this process with SDG.

However, since the method described above does not interpret conditional expressions in each node and decide that all paths are executable, some false warnings (which are actually not bugs) could be reported. Figure 7 gives examples of false warnings. In (a), “b = a + 5” can be detected as an use of uninitialized variables since “a = 0” is under a control node “if(1)”, although “a = 0” is always executed. On the other hand, in (b), ‘b = a + 5’ also can be

```

N1, N2, N : nodes in SDG
V : a variable in SDG
foreach N1 in assignment nodes {
  foreach V in variables used in N1 {
    foreach N2 in assignment nodes such that (
      (N2 is reachable from N1 only with data dependence edge) and
      (V is defined at N2) ){
      if exist N such that (
        (N is not ‘par’ nor ‘if’) and
        (N1 is reachable from N only with control dependence edge) and
        (N2 is reachable from N only with control dependence edge without
        passing control node) ){
        // variable V at N1 is initialized at N2
        next V
      }
    }
    display warning message
  }
}

```

Figure 6: Pseudo-code of uninitialized variable checking algorithm.

detected as an use of uninitialized variables since “a = 0” and “a = 1” are under a control node “if(cond)”, although always either “a = 0” or “a = 1” is executed. Such false warning problems are solved by interpreting conditional expressions in control nodes and checking reachabilities of initializing nodes formally by validity checkers.

Figure 8 gives an algorithm to get a conditional expression to judge whether the target node is reachable (which means really executed). This method works as follows :

1. Control / call edges are traversed backwardly until reaching a call-site of “main” function.
2. All conditional expressions of control nodes passed through are gathered, and their product is computed. (A control node “IF / ELSE” is considered as “IF” when it reaches the node via control edge of “True”, in the other case that reaches via “False”, it is considered as “ELSE”).
3. The satisfiability of the product is checked with a validity checker such as CVC[Stump et al. 2002].

The validity checker statically decides whether the condition is feasible by decision procedure. If the condition is feasible, the node is judged to be reachable, and it means that there are some input patterns with which a statement corresponding to the node is executed. If the condition is not feasible, it is proved that there are no input patterns with which the statement is executed. The result is the same as that of trying all input patterns by simulation. Though the method consumes more time than one simulation run, completeness of the result is a big advantage.

Figure 7: Examples of false warnings

With this method, the algorithm to detect uninitialized variables will be improved. Figure 9 gives the pseudo-code of the algorithm. In this pseudo-code, a function “eval()” means “evaluates the argument predicate, and returns true if the predicate is always satisfied”. In our implementation, we used a validity checker CVC[Stump et al. 2002] to perform the function.

3.1.3 Detection of Null Pointer Dereferences

Null pointer dereferences happen when a pointer variable pointing nothing is dereferenced. Normally, pointer variables are used after initializations which assign addresses of something. Null pointer dereferences are classified into three types as given in Figure 10. In each case, a pointer variable “p” is used at “b = *p + 5”. However, in (a), there are no nodes initializing “p” except for “p = NULL”. In (b), though “p = &a” initializes “p”, it may not be executed since it is under a conditional branch “if(cond)”. In (c), the execution order of “p = &a” and “b = *p + 5” is not decidable when behaviors “B31” and “B32” are running concurrently. Therefore, “p” can be dereferenced as null pointer in each case.

Null pointer dereferences can be detected by the following procedure.

1. For each pointer variable used in nodes, nodes which initialize the pointer are collected by traversing data dependence edges backwardly.
2. Whether there are no nodes initializing to null is checked.

```

expression GetReachableCondition_Local(node V){
expression result = "true";
bool reach_end = false;

while(!reach_end){
/* Traverse Control Dependence Edge Backwards */
switch(getNodeType(V = ParentViaControlEdge(V))){
case ENTRY: // If it reaches to ENTRY node, finish.
reach_end = true; break;
case IF:
case WHILE:
case FOR:
/* Add the expression of the node to the result */
result = (result && getExpr(V)); break;
case ELSE:
/* Add negation of the expression of the node to the result */
result = (result && !getExpr(V)); break;
case PAR:
/* do nothing */
result = result; break;
}
}
return result;
}

expression GetReachableCondition(node V){
expression result = "true";
bool reach_end = false;

while(!reach_end){
/* Traverse Control Edge or Call Edge Backwards */
switch(getNodeType(V)){
case MAIN_CALL_SITE: /* finish if call-site node of main() */
reach_end = true; break;
default:
result = (result && LocalReachability(V)); break;
}
V = GetCaller(GetEntry(V)); /* Find caller of current function */
}
return result;
}
}

```

Figure 8: Pseudo-code of an algorithm to get a conditional expression.

For example, a node “ $b = *p + 5$ ” in Figure 10 (b) is checked as follows.

1. A pointer variable “ p ” is used in the node.
2. Whether “ p ” can be null at the node is checked.
 - (a) Dependence edges about “ p ” are traversed backwardly from “ $b = *p + 5$ ”, and “ $p = \text{NULL}$ ” and “ $p = \&a$ ” are found as nodes initializing “ p ”
 - (b) Since there is a node where “ p ” is defined to null, “ p ” is found to have a possibility to be null.

Figure 11 gives an algorithm of this procedure with SDG.

In the null pointer dereferencing detection, the false warning problem mentioned in Section 3.1.2 may happen. Then, the reachability analysis technique proposed in Section 3.1.2 also can be applied to solve the problem.

```

N1, N2, N : nodes in SDG
V : a variable in SDG
foreach N1 in assignment nodes {
  foreach V in variables used in N1 {
    foreach N2 in assignment nodes such that (
      (N1 is reachable from N2 only with data dependence edge) and
      (V is defined at N2) ){

      if exist N such that (
        (N is not 'par' nor 'if') and
        (eval(GetReachableCondition(N2))
         -> GetReachableCondition(N1)) == true)
      ){

        // variable V at N1 is initialized at N2
        next V
      }
    }
  }
  display warning message
}
}

```

Figure 9: Pseudo-code of uninitialized variable checking algorithm using conditions of control nodes.

3.1.4 Detection of Deadlocks

Deadlocks occur when all concurrent processes are suspended and their executions cannot proceed any more. In SpecC designs, deadlocks are caused in the condition that a suspended process by a wait node is not resumed by at least one of the notify nodes connected with the wait node through data dependence edges. Therefore, deadlocks are detected by checking whether at least one of the corresponding notify nodes is executed for each wait node.

Figure 12 gives an example source code and its SDG for the deadlock detection. For simple introduction, several nodes and edges such as Formal In/Out nodes and edges connected with them are removed. In the example, there is a wait node “wait(e)” in a behavior “B2”. The deadlock checking for “wait(e)” starts from collecting corresponding notify nodes by backwardly traversing data dependence edges about “e”, and then a corresponding notify node “notify(e)” in a behavior “B1” is found. Next, whether “notify(e)” nodes exist in each path of “B1” is checked. In the example a “notify(e)” is in the “then” path of “if(cond)”, and no “notify(e)” exists in the “else” path of “if(cond)”. Therefore, we can say that deadlocks may occur in this case.

Figure 13 gives the algorithm to detect deadlocks with SDG.

3.1.5 Detection of Race Conditions

Race conditions occur if shared variables are accessed by concurrent processes without proper synchronizations and the computation results are dependent on the execution orders of the accesses. Race conditions can be detected by checking

Figure 10: Classification of null-pointer dereferences

```
N1, N2 : nodes in SDG
p : a pointer variable in SDG
foreach N1 in assignment nodes using pointer variables {
  foreach p in pointer variables dereferenced in N1 {
    foreach N2 in assignment nodes such that (
      (N1 is reachable from N2 only with data dependence edge of p)
      and
      (p is defined at N2)
    ){
      if ( p is defined NULL at N2 ){
        // pointer variable p at N1 has the possibility to be NULL
        display warning message
      }
    }
  }
}
```

Figure 11: Pseudo-code of null pointer dereference checking algorithm.

Figure 12: An example for deadlock detection

whether each execution order of two nodes connected by data dependence edges between concurrent processes is decidable or not.

In the race condition detection, we have to decide whether the execution order of two nodes in concurrent processes is decidable or not. Here, we can assume that deadlocks do not occur, since we can find them by the deadlock detection method proposed in Section 3.1.4. The conditions that a node “a” in a process “B1” must be executed before a node “b” in a process “B2” are as follows (See Figure 14):

- There are notify nodes “n”s after “a” for all paths in “B1”.
- There are wait nodes “w” s before “b” for all paths in “B2”.
- All pairs of an “n” and a “w” are connected through data dependence edges.
- There are no notify nodes except for those “n”s connected to those “w”s by data dependence edges. It guarantees that “B2” suspended by the “w”s is resumed only by the “n”s.

Figure 15 gives an example source code and its SDG for the race condition detection. In this case, there is a data dependence edge from “x = 0” in “B1” to “x = 2 * x” in “B2”. The race condition checking for the two nodes is carried out as follows. First, with assuming that “x = 0” is always executed before “x = 2 * x”, whether at least one notify node exists in all paths of “B1” is checked. However, this assumption is found false since notify nodes do not exist in the path after “x = 0”. Similarly, the assumption that “x = 2 * x” is always executed before “x = 0” is found false. Therefore, since the execution order of the two nodes is not decidable, we can say they are in race condition.

```

N1, N2, N3, N4, N5 : nodes in SDG
e : a event variable in SDG
foreach N1 in "wait" nodes {
  foreach e in event variables used in N1 {
    foreach N2 such that(
      (N2 is "notify" node) and
      (N1 is reachable from N2 only with data dependence edge of e)
    ){
      if (N2 does not exist){
        display warning message
        Next e
      }
      if(
        (exist N3 such that
          (N3 is "par" node) and
          (N1 is reachable from N3 only with control dependence edge) and
          (N2 is reachable from N3 only with control dependence edge) and
          not (exist N4 such that
            (N1 is reachable from N4 only with control dependence edge) and
            (N2 is reachable from N4 only with control dependence edge) and
            (N4 is reachable from N3 only with control dependence edge)
          )
        )
        and
        (exist N5 such that
          (N5 is "if", "while" or "for" node) and
          (N5 is reachable from N3 only with control dependence edge) and
          (N2 is reachable from N5 only with control dependence edge)
        )
      ){
        display warning message
        Next e
      }
    }
  }
}

```

Figure 13: Pseudo-code of deadlock checking algorithm.

Figure 14: An example SDG for race condition detection

Figure 15: An example for race condition detection

Figure 16 gives the algorithm to detect race conditions with SDG.

3.2 Hardware / Software Partitioning

After applying static checking methods to input descriptions, HW/SW partitioning is performed. As we mentioned in Section 2.4, though there are a lot of existing partitioning methods using heuristics, those methods can be applied only when designs have been divided into tasks(multiple procedures). Those tasks can be considered as behaviors in SpecC descriptions. To apply such partitioning methods flexibly, it is important to divide the designs into multiple behaviors executed concurrently.

In this section, we propose a method to divide a behavior into multiple concurrent behaviors by dependence analysis with SDG. In this method, parallelism is extracted via SDGs in a way such that two nodes can be executed in parallel wherever they don't depend on each other. Also, even if two nodes depend on each other, they can be assigned to separate concurrent behaviors by adding synchronization statements. This method can be applied to any sequential execution in a design.

Figure 17, 18 and 19 give an example. In this example, lines 9 to 14 in Figure 17 are the target to be divided. Figure 18 gives the SDG of this code (control edges are abbreviated).

We divide this code into two behaviors. Suppose “ $x8 = W7*(x4+x5);$ ”, “ $x5 = x8 - (W1+W7)*x5;$ ”, and “ $x6 = x8 - (W3-W5)*x6;$ ” are assigned to one behavior, and others are assigned to another (This partitioning is very inefficient,

```

N1, N2, N3, N4, N5, N6, N7: nodes in SDG
V : a variable in SDG
foreach N1 in declaration nodes of shared variables {
  foreach V in variables declared in N1 {
    foreach N2 and N3 in assignment nodes{
      if (
        (N2 and N3 are not the same node) and
        (N2 and N3 has a data dependence about V) and
        (exist N4 such that
          (N4 is "par" node) and
          (N2 is reachable from N4 only with control dependence edge) and
          (N3 is reachable from N4 only with control dependence edge) and
          not (exist N5 such that
            (N2 is reachable from N5 only with control dependence edge) and
            (N2 is reachable from N5 only with control dependence edge) and
            (N5 is reachable from N4 only with control dependence edge)
          )
        )
      )
      and not
      (
        ((exist N6 such that
          (N6 is "wait" node) and
          (N2 is reachable from N6 only with control dependence edge)
        )
        and
        (exist N7 such that
          (N7 is "notify" node) and
          (Argument in N7 is the same as that in N6) and
          (N7 is reachable form N3 only with control flow edge)
        ))
      )
      or
      ((exist N6 such that
        (N6 is "wait" node) and
        (N3 is reachable from N6 only with control dependence edge)
      )
      and
      (exist N7 such that
        (N7 is "notify" node) and
        (Argument in N7 is the same as that in N6) and
        (N7 is reachable form N2 only with control flow edge)
      ))
    )
  )
}{
  display warning message
  Next pair of N2 and N3
}
}
}
}

```

Figure 16: Pseudo-code of race condition checking algorithm.

```

1  const int W1,W2,W3,W4,          10  x4 = x8 + (W1-W7)*x4;
2  W5,W6,W7,W8;                  11  x5 = x8 - (W1+W7)*x5;
3  (snip)                          12  x8 = W3*(x6+x7);
4  behavior IDCT(){               13  x6 = x8 - (W3-W5)*x6;
5  (snip)                          14  x7 = x8 - (W3+W5)*x7;
6  void idct_row(void){           15  (snip)
7  int x4,x5,x6,x7,x8;            16  }
8  (snip)                          17  };
9  x8 = W7*(x4+x5);

```

Figure 17: Example of partitioning.

Figure 18: An example SDG of partitioning.

```

1  const int W1,W2,W3,W4,          37  (snip)
2      W5,W6,W7,W8;              38
3  behavior B1(                   39  behavior IDCT(){
4      int x4,int x5,int x6,       40      int x4_b,x5_b,x6_b,x7_b,x8_b;
5      int x7,int x8,             41      event e1,e2;
6      event e1,event e2){       42      B1 b1(x4_b,x5_b,x6_b,
7                                  43          x7_b,x8_b,e1,e2);
8      void main(void){          44      B2 b2(x4_b,x5_b,x6_b,
9          int x8_local;          45          x7_b,x8_b,e1,e2);
10         x8_local = W7*(x4+x5);  46      (snip)
11         x8 = x8_local;         47      void idct_row(void){
12         notify e1;            48          int x4,x5,x6,x7,x8;
13         x5 = x8_local-(W1+W7)*x5;  49
14         wait e2;              50
15         x8_local = x8;        51      (snip)
16         x6 = x8_local-(W3-W5)*x6;  52
17     }                          53      x4_b=x4;
18 };                              54      x5_b=x5;
19                                  55      x6_b=x6;
20  behavior B2(                   56      x7_b=x7;
21      int x4,int x5,int x6,       57      x8_b=x8;
22      int x7,int x8,             58      par{
23      event e1,event e2){       59          b1.main();
24                                  60          b2.main();
25      void main(void){          61      }
26          int x8_local;         62      x4=x4_b;
27          wait e1;              63      x5=x5_b;
28          x8_local = x8;        64      x6=x6_b;
29          x4 = x8_local+(W1-W7)*x4;  65      x7=x7_b;
30          x8_local = W3*(x6+x7);  66      x8=x8_b;
31          x8 = x8_local;        67
32          notify e2;           68      (snip)
33          x7 = x8_local-(W3+W5)*x7;  69
34      }                          70      }
35 };                              71 };
36

```

Figure 19: Example of partitioning (Result).

but just an example). Since “ $x6=x8-(W3-W5)*x6$ ” in Behavior1 depends on “ $x8=W3*(x6+x7)$ ” in Behavior2, and “ $x4=x8+(W1-W7)*x4$ ” in Behavior2 depends on “ $x8=W7*(x4+x5)$ ” in Behavior1, synchronization statements should be inserted. Also, variable “ $x8$ ” is used in both behaviors, so this variable should be copied in each behavior (This problem will easily resolved with static single assignment representation and is just a minor problem). As a result, we get a code shown in figure 19. This code is generated automatically with the following algorithm.

1. New behaviors B_1, B_2, \dots, B_n are created (n is a preset maximum number of concurrent processes)
 2. The selected statements are distributed to each behavior.
 - Some of the selected statements are added to the function main of B_1 .
 - Some of the other selected statements are added to the function main of B_2 .
 - ...
 - The other selected statements are added to the function main of B_n .
 3. Behaviors to which no statements are added are removed.
4. For each combination of i and j ($1 \leq i \leq n - r, 1 \leq j \leq n - r, i < j$, where r is the number of removed behaviors), the following procedure is applied.
 - For each data dependence edge from a node N_1 in B_i to a node N_2 in B_j , the following procedure is applied.
 - A variable V defined at node N_1 is renamed to V_local in B_i and B_j . A declaration of V_local is added to B_1 and B_2 .
 - A declaration of a new event variable e_k is added to the original behavior for the synchronization about V .
 - Statements “ $V = V_local;$ ” and “ $notify(e_k);$ ” are added before N_1 .
 - “ $wait(e_k);$ ” and “ $V_local = V;$ ” are added before N_2 .
 - For each data dependence edge from N_2 to N_1 the same procedure is applied.
 - For each variable V used in B_i or B_j , a declaration of a variable V_b is added to the original behavior.
 - Instantiations of B_i and B_j is added to the original behavior. Their arguments are the event variables (e_n) and behavior variables (V_b).
5. In the original behavior, the selected statements are replaced with:

- Assignments such as “ $V_b = V;$ ” for each V_b
- Function calls of new behaviors’ main functions under a **par** statement such as “ $\text{par}\{b1.main(); b2.main()\}$ ”.
- Assignments such as “ $V = V_b;$ ” for each V_b

We apply this process to each assignment candidate exhaustively. Let l be the number of statements in the target description, and n be the maximum number of concurrent behaviors to be generated. Then the number of generated descriptions become $l^n - l$ ($-l$ are the case when no statement is assigned to one of the behaviors). In the example given in Figure 17, since the target include 6 statements and each statement is assigned to one of the two behaviors, $2^6 - 2 = 62$ descriptions are generated.

When the target code has a lot of statements or the maximum number of concurrent behaviors is set to a large number, the number of generated descriptions becomes huge. However, those descriptions include meaningless cases. For example, the case that a large numbers of data transitions and synchronizations are added. In such a case, the performance must be bad. We can exclude them by restricting the numbers of data transitions and synchronizations.

The generated descriptions can be partitioned into HW and SW, and evaluated with existing methods [Ueda et al. 2005] or tools such as SCE [SCE]. Our code generation and those evaluations can be performed automatically. Therefore designers can try many patterns of partitioning and can choose the proper one.

After the partitioning we may have to merge the behaviors assigned to SW or HW. For example, in the case when we do not execute SW on a multi task OS, we have to merge concurrent behaviors assigned to SW into a single behavior. This process can be performed with a sequentialization method proposed in [Sakunkonchak et al. 2007]. In the method, after applying synchronization verification, concurrent behaviors are converted into one sequential behavior.

The parts assigned to HW can be optimized more, and then synthesized into RTL by existing behavioral synthesis tools.

3.3 Formal Checking with FSM

Further to HW behavioral synthesis, we must ensure logical equivalences between original descriptions and descriptions after HW synthesis. Also, designers may want to statically verify the latter descriptions. However, the latter descriptions are different from the original ones in two points. One is that HW parts and SW parts in the latter descriptions are described in the different levels (behavioral level and RTL). The other is that they communicate through Memory-mapped I/O or by Interrupt-driven I/O. These points make verification difficult. Usually, such co-designs are verified by HW/SW co-simulation [Seamless], but it is impossible to test all input patterns.

Figure 20: Formal checking with FSM

We therefore propose a method to verify the descriptions after HW synthesis by formal verification. Currently, formal methods introduced in Section 2.5 cannot be directly applied to the descriptions, since the descriptions have the two features mentioned above. Then, we resolve this problem by converting HW/SW descriptions into communication abstracted FSMs. In the FSMs, HW parts and SW parts in each design are combined into a single FSM and verified together. We apply model checking, and also equivalence checking between the original descriptions to them.

There are two reasons to translate those descriptions into FSMs. Firstly, formal verification for FSMs (and RTL descriptions) is a matured technique, and there are many stable model checkers and equivalence checkers for them. Secondly, HW descriptions are normally written in RTL which is the same abstraction level as FSM. By identifying registers with state variables, RTL descriptions can be easily translated into FSMs.

Here we restrict the verification target to designs whose HW parts and SW parts communicate through Memory-mapped I/O. Interfaces generated by our methods have corresponding variables in the HW parts and the SW parts. In Memory-mapped I/O, HW registers are assigned to particular addresses in a SW address space, and the correspondences between HW registers and SW addresses are already known. Pointer accesses are used to send and receive data in the SW.

Figure 20 gives the main steps of our formal checking process.

First, SW descriptions in the designs after HW synthesis are translated into FSMs as shown in the left-hand side in Figure 21. This example is the SW part of Figure 19 when the behavior B1 is assigned to SW. The SW descriptions are converted into descriptions only composed of assignments, "if", and "while" statements. Namely, replacements of local pointers with variables, "for" statements with "while" statements, "case" statements with "if" statements, decompositions of structures, and so on, have been performed. Then, the descriptions

Figure 21: Translation from C to FSM

are translated into FSMs as one assignment is mapped to one state. Conditional expressions in "if" and "while" statements become conditions of state transition branches. Additionally, pointers to addresses to where HW registers are assigned are replaced with corresponding HW registers.

Next, HW descriptions in the designs after HW synthesis are translated into FSMs. As previously mentioned, RTL descriptions can be easily translated into FSMs by identifying registers with state variables. Also, a part of HW where data from the bus is assigned to the registers corresponding to the SW addresses, are separated from the entire HW parts. The separated part can be independently verified because it is not directly associated with the original design. This verification is easy, since the part is usually small and simple. If it has been verified in advance, then The correctness of the communications through Memory-mapped I/O is guaranteed. An example of HW FSMs is shown at the right-hand side in Figure 21. This example is the HW part of Figure 19 when the behavior B2 is assigned to HW.

As a result, the HW/SW descriptions are translated into pairs of concurrent FSMs communicating through HW registers as shared variables.

Then, we convert them into sets of sequential FSMs. As there can be two or more execution orders in the concurrent FSMs, for each execution order, states in a pair of concurrent FSMs are sorted out, and combined to a single sequential FSM. We must do this procedure for all possible execution orders to make the verification exhaustive. However, we do not have to consider all execution orders of states where

- there are no data transitions between HW and SW.
- their execution orders can be statically determined by synchronizations.

For example, in Figure 21 (c) and (d), we do not have to consider the execution order of states s_6 and s_d , since the results are the same. Also, s_1 must be executed before s_b , since there is synchronization with a variable $E1$. Therefore, we can convert concurrent FSMs to a practical number of sequential FSMs. Such data transitions or synchronization between HW and SW can be found as data

Figure 22: FSMs at the final step

dependence edges or control dependence edges, respectively among concurrent processes in the SDGs of the original descriptions.

Besides, we can merge assignment statements among which there are no data dependencies, and eliminate states for synchronizations since sequential executions do not have to synchronize any more. The data dependencies can also be found as data dependence edges in the SDGs of original descriptions. The generated FSMs are not much complicated because these are essentially sequential. Also, the numbers of states in them are relatively not large after merging states. These can formally be verified with existing model checkers after describing it in the model checkers' input language. An example is given in Figure 22. The right FSM is generated from the FSMs (c) and (d) in Figure 21. When more than one FSM is generated, all of them should be model checked, and only if all of them passed the checks, the correctness of the design is guaranteed.

Additional translations are required to equivalence check with the original descriptions and the descriptions after HW synthesis. The original descriptions are translated into FSMs in the same way as the previously mentioned C-to-FSM translation methods. The left FSM in Figure 22 is the example from the lines 39-14 in Figure 17. Then, the problems have been reduced to equivalence checking of two different designs described in the same representation. Equivalence checking must be performed with all pairs of two designs' FSMs.

4 Case Study and Experimental Result

In this section, we show how to apply the proposed methodology to HW/SW co-designs of an MPEG2 decoder and a JPEG2000 encoder to demonstrate the usefulness of our approach. Experimental results of each step are also reported to show the performances of them. These experiments have been executed on a workstation with two 3.2Hz processors and 4GB memory.

4.1 Examples

We used an MPEG2 decoder(MPEG2)[mssg], and a JPEG2000 encoder[j2000] as examples. Both examples are written in C and their numbers of lines are shown in the second column of Table 2.

Table 2: Information of the original C codes

Example	# of lines in C	SDG generation time by [Grammatech]
MPEG2	7600	11.541 sec
JPEG2000	4300	5.827 sec

Table 3: Information of SpecC test-case codes.

Example	# of lines in SpecC	# of nodes in SDG	SDG gen. time	# of nodes in HW
IDCT	135	389	1.685 sec	312
DWT	202	1474	3.312 sec	1451

4.2 Code Extraction

First, we tried to extract codes as candidates of HW/SW co-designs. We found that heavy calculations are processed at Inverse Discrete Cosine Transform (IDCT) in MPEG2 and Discrete Wavelet Transform (DWT) in JPEG2000. We therefore extracted the codes which process those calculations from the entire codes. This process was done by chopping, and we successfully extracted codes related to the IDCT functions and DWT functions with a commercial program slicer CodeSurfer[Grammatech]. We applied chopping as follows.

- First, backward slicing from the output of the function `Fast_IDCT()`, and forward slicing from the input of the same function is applied. Next, the product of those results is extracted.
- First, backward slicing from the output of the function `dwt_encode()`, and forward slicing from the input of the same function is applied. Next, the product of those results is extracted.

The SDG generation times are shown in the third column of Table 2. In both cases, chopping finished within 1 second.

Next, we translated the IDCT and DWT codes into SpecC descriptions. In this process, parallelism was introduced to the IDCT code. We created SDGs of those SpecC descriptions by the method proposed in [Tanabe et al. 2004]. The sizes of the descriptions and SDGs are shown in Table 3. These descriptions are treated as original descriptions in the subsequent steps.

4.3 Static Program Checking

As the flow given in Figure 3, we first applied the static program checking methods proposed in Section 3.1. Each checking method was performed by a tool we had developed. The results are shown in Table 4. Whether the detected warnings are real ones was confirmed by the authors. These results show, (1) node interpretation makes false-warnings less, and, (2) The number of CVC calling affects directly on processing time.

We modified the detected errors for the further steps.

Table 4: Experimental results of program checking

Type of Check	Use validity checker	Test-case	Warnings	Real errors	False warnings	Miss	Time (sec)	# of CVC callings
Unused	No	IDCT	4	4	0	0	0.068	-
		DWT	11	1	10	0	0.176	-
Uninitialized	No	IDCT	48	2	46	0	0.082	-
		DWT	28	1	27	0	0.228	-
	Yes	IDCT	3	2	1	0	1.341	77
		DWT	11	1	10	0	1.119	56
Null Pointer	No	IDCT	3	2	1	0	0.067	-
		DWT	2	1	1	0	0.169	-
	Yes	IDCT	2	2	0	0	0.103	2
		DWT	1	1	0	0	0.207	2
Deadlock	No	IDCT	9	9	0	0	0.168	-
Race Condition	No	IDCT	144	144	0	0	0.279	-

4.4 HW/SW Partitioning

As the second step, we applied the HW/SW partitioning methods proposed in Section 3.2.

First, we tried to extract parallelism for each example. For this purpose, we developed a parallelism extraction tool. It can automatically generate parallelized codes exhaustively under preset conditions. Currently, we can set the number of parallel processes and the maximum number of output descriptions. The code generations were performed in quite a short time. For example, 256 codes were generated from IDCT in a second. We selected the codes whose amount of data transitions are minimum.

Next, we partitioned each parallel process (behavior) to HW or SW. In IDCT, 16 processes were assigned to HW, and 1 was assigned to SW. In DWT, 1 process was assigned to HW, and 1 process was assigned to SW. These partitionings were done by hand. The numbers of nodes in the SDGs assigned to HW are shown in the fifth column in Table 3. The other nodes were assigned to SW.

After the partitioning, the HW parts were synthesized into RTL Verilog descriptions. Though this could be done with existing behavioral synthesis tools, we did it by hand.

4.5 Formal Verification

As the last step, we applied the formal verification method proposed in Section 3.3.

First, we converted those examples into FSMs as given in Figure 20 and tried to verify by a model checker NuSMV [Cimatti et al. 2002] directly. However, the examples are so large that we could not even estimate the number of states.

Therefore, we abstracted the FSMs by changing the bit-width of each data register to 1. The sizes of the abstracted FSMs are shown in Table 5. The second column shows the numbers of states in the abstracted FSMs. It does not show the number of states in Kripke structure, since multi-bit variables (registers) have not been decomposed. The numbers of states variables (flip-flops) and states in Kripke structure are shown in the third and fourth columns, respectively.

Table 5: Verification results of formal verification

Example	# of states in Kripke structure	# of state variables	# of states in Kripke structure	verification bound	verification time
IDCT	17	579	1.98×10^{174}	30 cycles	72 sec
DWT	15	812	2.73×10^{244}	100 cycles	369 sec

The numbers showing states in Kripke structure are just estimations, since the abstracted FSMs are still too large to analyze reachable states exhaustively.

Finally, we applied Bounded Model Checking(BMC)[Biere et al. 1999] to the abstracted FSMs with a property “The calculation eventually finishes” by NuSMV . Each abstracted FSM has a state variable which shows the current state. Let s be the state variable and n be the value of the final state, then the property can be written as “ $F(s = n)$ ” in Linear Temporal Logic (LTL). The results of this property are not different in the FSMs and the abstracted FSMs, since it is only related to the control-flow and not to the data-flow. We applied BMC instead of normal symbolic model checking[McMillan 1993], since it can handle larger designs.

The bounds of BMC and verification times are shown in the fifth and sixth column, respectively in Table 5. The results show that the method proposed in Section 3.3 can verify practical designs within practical times.

5 Conclusion

In this paper, we proposed a HW/SW co-design methodology based on SDG.

In the method, input C / C++ / SpecC descriptions are checked by program checking, partitioned into HW and SW, and formally verified after HW synthesis.

In the program checking, five types of typical design errors are detected by traversing dependence edges in SpecC SDGs. In the HW/SW partitioning, parallelism extraction is performed in statement granularity by analyzing data dependencies with the SDGs. This means that each statement may independently be partitioned into HW or SW, and more flexible than existing methods. Also, in the formal verification, HW and SW parts are translated and integrated to sequential FSMs to verify them with existing formal verifiers. Number of states and sequential FSMs are reduced by analyzing data and control dependencies with the SDGs.

In the case studies of an MPEG2 encoder and a JPEG2000 encoder, each step was processed in a short time. It shows the usefulness of the proposed methodology.

The proposed methodology places an emphasis on verification and parallelism extraction in a fine granularity. These points have been received low priorities in existing design methodologies or tools such as SCE[SCE], and the proposed methodology can supplement the weaknesses. Therefore, we can archive more secure and flexible SoC design systems by integrating the proposed methodology with the existing design methodologies.

Acknowledgements

Authors thank the anonymous referees for their valuable comments.

References

- [Biere et al. 1999] Biere, A., A.Cimatti, Clarke, E. M., and Y.Zhu (1999). Symbolic model checking without bdds. In *Proc. of the International Conference on Tools and Algorithms for the Construction and Analysis of Systems*, pages 193–207.
- [Brand 1993] Brand, D. (1993). Verification of large synthesized designs. In *Proc. of the International Conference on Computer Aided Design*, pages 534–537.
- [Cimatti et al. 2002] Cimatti, A., Clarke, E. M., Giunchiglia, E., Giunchiglia, F., Pistore, M., Roveri, M., Sebastiani, R., , and Tacchella, A. (2002). Nusmv 2: An open-source tool for symbolic model checking. In *Proc. of the International Conference on Computer Aided Verification*, pages 359–364.
- [Clarke et al. 2003] Clarke, E., Kroening, D., and Yorav, K. (2003). Behavioral consistency of c and verilog programs using bounded model checking. In *Proc. of the Design Automation Conference*, pages 368–371.
- [Clarke et al. 1986] Clarke, E. M., Emerson, E. A., and Sistla, A. P. (1986). Automatic verification of finite-state concurrent systems using temporal logic specifications. *ACM Trans. on Programming Languages and Systems*, 8(2):244–263.
- [Clarke et al. 1999] Clarke, E. M., Fujita, M., Rajan, S. P., Reps, T. W., Shankar, S., and Teitelbaum, T. (1999). Program slicing of hardware description languages. In *Conference on Correct Hardware Design and Verification Methods*, pages 298–312.
- [Coverity] Coverity. <http://www.coverity.com/>.
- [Ferrante et al. 1987] Ferrante, J., Ottenstein, K. J., and Warren, J. D. (1987). The program dependence graph and its use in optimization. *ACM Trans. Program. Lang. Syst.*, 9(3):319–349.
- [FlexeLint] FlexeLint. <http://www.gimpel.com/>.
- [Formality] Formality. <http://www.synopsys.com/products/verification/verification.html>.
- [Fortify] Fortify. <http://www.fortifysoftware.com/products/sca.jsp>.
- [Grammatech] Codesurfer. <http://www.grammatech.com/products/codesurfer/>.
- [Grobe et al. 2003] Grobe, D. and Drechsler, R. (2003). Formal verification of ltl formulas for systemc designs. In *Proc. of the International Symposium on Circuits and Systems*, pages 245–248.
- [Grobe et al. 2004] Grobe, D. and Drechsler, R. (2004). Checkers for systemc designs. In *Proc. of the International Conference on Formal Methods and Models for Codesign*, pages 171–178.
- [Holzmann 2002] Holzmann, G. J. (2002). Uno: Static source code checking for user-defined properties. In *Proc. of World Conference on Integrated Design and Process Technology*, pages 26–30.
- [j2000] j2000.org. <http://j2000.org/>.
- [Karfa et al. 2006] Karfa, C., Mandal, M., Sarkar, D., Pentakota, S. R., and Reade, C. (2006). A formal verification method of scheduling in high-level synthesis. In *Proc. of the International Symposium on Quality Electronic Design*, pages 110–115.
- [Knerr et al. 2004] Knerr, B., Holzer, M., and M.Rupp (2004). Hw/sw partitioning using high level metrics. In *Proc. of International Conference on Computing, Communications and Control Technologies*, pages 33–39.
- [Kuehlmann et al. 2002] Kuehlmann, A. and van Eijk, C. A. J. (2002). *Logic Synthesis and Verification*, chapter 13, pages 343–372. Kluwer Academic Publishers.
- [Matsumoto et al. 2006] Matsumoto, T., Saito, H., and Fujita, M. (2006). Equivalence checking of c programs by locally performing symbolic simulation on dependence graphs. In *Proc. of the International Symposium on Quality of Electronic Design*, pages 370–375.

- [McMillan 1993] McMillan, K. L. (1993). *Symbolic model checking - an approach to the state explosion problem*. Kluwer Academic Publishers.
- [Moy et al. 2005] Moy, M., Maraninchi, F., and Contoz, L. M. (2005). Lussy: A toolbox for the analysis of systems-on-a-chip at the transactional level. In *Proc. of the International Conference on Application of Concurrency to System Design*, pages 26–35.
- [mssg] Mpeg software simulation group. <http://www.mpeg.org/MPEG/MSSG/>.
- [Orion] Orion. <http://cm.bell-labs.com/cm/cs/what/orion/>.
- [Saito et al. 2002] Saito, H., Ogawa, T., Sakunkonchak, T., Fujita, M., and Nanya, T. (2002). An equivalence checking methodology for hardware oriented c-based specification. In *Proc. of International Workshop on High Level Design Varidation and Test*, pages 139–144.
- [Sakunkonchak et al. 2005] Sakunkonchak, T., Komatsu, S., and Fujita, M. (2005). Synchronization verification in system-level design with ilp solvers. In *Proc. of the Formal Methods and Models for Co-Design*, pages 121–130.
- [Sakunkonchak et al. 2007] Sakunkonchak, T., Matsumoto, T., Saito, H., Komatsu, S., and Fujita, M. (2007). Equivalence checking in c-based system-level design by sequentializing concurrent behaviors. In *Proc. of International Conference on Advances in Computer Science and Technology*, pages 36–42.
- [Sasaki et al. 2006] Sasaki, S., Nishihara, T., and Fujita, M. (2006). Slicing based hardware/software co-design methodology from functional specifications. *Electric Notes in Theoretical Computer Science*, 159:265–280.
- [SCE] System-on-chip design environment (sce). <http://www.cecs.uci.edu/~cad/projects.html>.
- [Seamless] Seamless. http://www.mentor.com/products/fv/hsw/_coverification/seamless/.
- [Semeria et al. 2002] Semeria, L., Seawright, A., Mehra, R., Ng, D., Ekanayake, A., and Pangrle, B. (2002). C-based RTL methodology for designing and verifying a multi-thread processor. In *Proc. of the Design Automation Conference*, pages 123–128.
- [SLEC] SLEC RTL. http://www.calypto.com/products/SLEC/_RTL.html.
- [Solidify] Solidify. <http://www.averant.com/products.htm>.
- [SpecC] SpecC. <http://www.cecs.uci.edu/~specc/>.
- [Stump et al. 2002] Stump, A., Barret, C., and Dill, D. (2002). Cvc: a cooperating validity checker. In *Proc. of 14th International Conference on Computer-Aided Verification*.
- [SystemC] SystemC. <http://www.systemc.org/>.
- [Tanabe et al. 2004] Tanabe, K., Sasaki, S., and Fujita, M. (2004). Program slicing for system level designs in specc. In *Proc. of the IASTED, International Conference on Advances in Computer Science and Technology*, pages 252–258.
- [Ueda et al. 2005] Ueda, K., Sakanushi, K., Takeuchi, Y., and M.Imai (2005). Architecture-level performance estimation method based on system-level profiling. *IEEE Proceedings Computers and Digital Techniques*, 152(1):12–19.
- [Weiser 1984] Weiser, M. (1984). Program slicing. *IEEE Transactions on Software Engineering*, 10(4):352–357.
- [Wiangtong et al. 2002] Wiangtong, T., Cheung, P., and Luk, W. (2002). Comparing three heuristic search methods for functional partitioning in hardware-software codesign. *Design Automation for Embedded Systems*, 6:425–429.